

THE USE OF INNOVATIVE METHODS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract: This article presents thoughts and practical considerations on the use of modern innovative technologies in teaching foreign languages and their effectiveness.

Keywords: foreign languages, innovative technologies, effectiveness, modern methods.

ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ИННОВАЦИОННЫХ МЕТОДОВ В ПРЕПОДАВАНИИ ИНОСТРАННЫХ ЯЗЫКОВ

Аннотация: В данной статье представлены размышления и практические соображения об использовании современных инновационных технологий в преподавании иностранных языков и их эффективности.

Ключевые слова: иностранные языки, инновационные технологии, эффективность, современные методы.

The 21st century is a time of rapid development of modern technologies, which is reflected in every sphere. In this globalized society, the demand for learning foreign languages is growing day by day.

In the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev dated May 19, 2021, "On Measures to Raise the Activities on Popularizing the Study of Foreign Languages in the Republic of Uzbekistan to a Qualitatively New Level", in accordance with the State Program "Year of Supporting Youth and Strengthening Public Health", special attention is paid to the development of teaching foreign languages as a priority area of educational policy, radically improving the quality of education in this area, attracting qualified teachers to the field, and increasing the population's interest in learning foreign languages. A new stage, a new era has begun in the teaching of foreign languages in our country.

The process of teaching foreign language lessons now requires the use of advanced pedagogical technologies, interactive and innovative methods, as well as communicative-information tools. In our republic, new methods and requirements for teaching foreign languages assessing foreign language teachers' knowledge and skills have been developed in accordance with the recommendations of the Common European Framework of Reference (CEFR). Consequently, new textbooks have been created for students in general education schools and vocational schools. In accordance with these requirements, classrooms were equipped with new information and communication technologies. The foreign language subject is divided into four aspects (reading, writing, listening understanding, and speaking), and separate concepts and skills are being taught for each of them.

The importance of advanced modern technologies in teaching foreign languages is invaluable. Indeed, the use of technological tools in the educational process plays a crucial role in the acquisition and reinforcement of knowledge in every aspect of foreign language learning. For example, it is impossible to develop listening comprehension skills without using computers, audio players, and CDs. Listening comprehension is one of the most essential

components of language learning. In this case, the student is simultaneously required to pay attention to the speaker's pronunciation, adherence to grammatical rules, vocabulary, and its meanings.

In today's globalization process, the internet has encompassed every aspect of our lives. Establishing the rational use of social networks and various websites for learning foreign languages among the younger generation has become a pressing issue. Especially communication with native speakers through the internet.

It is possible to develop speaking skills and improve the practice of writing by corresponding via e-mail. The importance of using multimedia tools in the educational process is invaluable. In particular, by organizing the lesson through slides, using methods that attract students to the beginning of the foreign language lesson (warm-up activities), using exhibitions of different colors, it is possible to achieve a meaningful organization of the lesson and the full assimilation of the topic by students. It has also been proven that organizing the educational process in schools through interactive games yields very positive results.

It is known that conducting a lesson based on various games not only reveals the possibilities of creative and critical thinking of students, but also develops their ability to concentrate and find ways out of problem situations. Because the basis of using games is activity that activates and accelerates the student. According to psychologists, playful the psychological mechanisms of activity are based on the fundamental needs of self-expression, finding a stable place in life, self-management, and realizing one's potential. Any game should be based on generally accepted educational principles and tactics. To educational games academic subjects should be taken as a basis. In the process of games, the student approaches this activity with more interest and behaves more freely than in a regular lesson.

This makes it especially easy to work with students who are naturally shy and unable to quickly integrate into the team. It plays an important role in improving their sociability abilities. It should be noted that play is, first of all, a method of teaching. Students participate in game lessons with interest, strive to win, and ultimately enrich their knowledge and skills. For example, during the process of participating in an English language game, the student strengthens their self-confidence and becomes motivated, thinking, "I can speak, listen, and write in this language".

We know that in the current educational process, the student should be the subject. In this case, using more interactive methods increases the effectiveness of education. One of the most important requirements for foreign language lessons is to teach students to think independently and creatively. Today, foreign language teachers in our republic, based on the experience of teachers from the United States of America and England, use the following innovative methods:

- "A chain story" method helps to develop students' oral speech;
- "Acting characters" - this method can be used in all types of lessons. For teaching the craft, people of such professions as "Interpreter", "Translator", "Writer", "Poet" can participate in the lesson and talk with students;
- "Thinkers Meeting" where poets and writers such as W. Shakespeare, A. Navoi, R. Burns can be "invited". In such cases, using their wise words in the lesson helps to nurture young people into well-rounded individuals;

– The “When Pictures Speak” method is quite convenient in teaching English, it helps develop students' oral speech, for which it is necessary to use topic-related pictures;

– Quiz cards are distributed according to the number of students and allow all students to participate in the lesson simultaneously, ensure attention is given to all students, and save time;

– Quiz cards are distributed according to the number of students and allow all students to participate in the lesson at the same time, ensure attention to all students, and save time.

Based on the foregoing, it can be concluded that each innovative technology has its own advantages. In all such methods, collaboration between teacher and student, active participation of the student in the educational process.

As a result of applying innovative technologies and methods in foreign language lessons, students develop logical and creative thinking skills, their speech becomes more fluent, and they form the ability to respond quickly and correctly. Organizing lessons using non-traditional methods and various techniques prevents boring activities. This creates a foundation for increasing interest in learning foreign languages and enthusiasm for acquiring knowledge among the younger generation, as well as for the effective organization of lessons. As a result, students come to class with thorough preparation, leading to a rapid increase in the effectiveness of their learning.

References:

Используемая литература:

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Gazieva, S.T. (2021). READING IS THE RECEPTIVE SIDE OF WRITING. ACADEMIC RESEARCH IN EDUCATIONAL SCIENCES. ARES, 2 (5), 1564- 1570.
2. MD Ismatullaevna, EG Yusupovich. the effectiveness of the use of information technology in the educational _rocess- european journal of research and reflection in, 2019
3. Ф. М. Муминова. — Текст: непосредственный // Молодойученый. — 2020. — № 18 (308). — С. 590-592. — URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/308/69404/> (датаобращения: 27.05.2022).
4. М. Р. Отабоева. — Текст: непосредственный, электронный // Молодойученый. — 2017. — № 4.2 (138.2). — С. 36-37. — URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/138/39058/>